

Synthesis, Structural and Magnetic Properties of Cobalt Ferrite (CoFe₂O₄) Nanoparticles by Simple Co-precipitation Technique

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Manuscript Details

Available online on <https://www.irjse.in>
ISSN: 2322-0015

Editor: Dr. Arvind Chavhan

Cite this article as:

Mhaske Sujit S, Kakade Sandip B, Thorat Sopan M, Kalange Ashok E. Synthesis, Structural and Magnetic Properties of Cobalt Ferrite (CoFe₂O₄) Nanoparticles by Simple Co-precipitation Technique, *Int. Res. Journal of Science & Engineering*, 2023, Special Issue A12: 11-14.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7763129>.

Article published in Special issue of International Conference on "Recent Trends in Materials Science, Synthesis, Characterization and Applications (RTMS-2023)" organized by Department of Physics, Anekant Education Society's, Tuljaram Chaturchand College of Arts, Science and Commerce, Baramati, Dist Pune, Maharashtra, India (Autonomous) date, January 3-4, 2023.

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Abstract

In the present work, phase pure Cobalt ferrite (CoFe₂O₄) nanoparticles are successfully synthesized by simple co-precipitation method. Structural and morphological properties of synthesized material are studied by X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) respectively. The results show that successfully formation of spherical nano particles with spinel crystalline structure. Strong peaks of Co, Fe and O are clearly observed in the EDX, which shows that the presence of these elements.

Keywords: Cobalt ferrite (CoFe₂O₄), nanoparticles, XRD, SEM, EDX

Introduction

Synthesis of magnetic nanomaterials research is particular to study optical, magnetic, electric properties [1,2] analyse to bulk materials. magnetic properties are built upon purity, shape and size of particles. Cobalt ferrite (CoFe₂O₄) nanoparticles are synthesised by Evaporation condensation [3], hot spraying, sol-gel [4], vapour phase reactions, thermal decomposition, hydrothermal Polly method [5], matrix isolation, co-precipitation method [6] etc. Co-precipitation method synthesised nanoparticles size of cobalt ferrite changes to variation of concentration, stirring speed, synthesis technique and temperature. [6-8]. Cobalt ferrite is widely used to sensors [9], solar cell [10], microwave absorber [11] and biomedical applications [12].

Spinel ferrite is mechanical hardness, moderate saturation, large coercivity, crystalline anisotropy and large cubic magnetisation at room temp [13]. In this paper we have synthesized cobalt ferrite nanoparticles by simple co-precipitation method at 80 °C. This method can be easily applied for bulk nanoparticle applications, such as for permanent magnets and biomedical applications.

Methodology

Synthesis of Cobalt ferrite (CoFe₂O₄) nanoparticles

The solution mixture of 50 ml of 1 M FeCl₃.6H₂O and 50 ml of 0.5 M CoCl₃.6H₂O and 7.5 M NaOH solution added by drop by drop up to pH 10-12. The solution is stirred for 45 minutes at 750 rpm at room temperature. The obtained precipitate of the solution is filtered out and washes five times with double distilled water. The obtained sample is dried in oven at 80 °C.

Characterisation:

Cobalt ferrite sample was characterised by X Ray Diffraction XRD (Bruker D8 Venture) to final material confirmed magnetic nanoparticle of CoFe₂O₄ with spinel Structured. Particle morphology is observed Scanning electron microscope SEM (FEI Nova Nano SEM 450).and composition of material identified by Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy EDX (Bruker X Flash 6130). FTIR study confirmed that phase formation its characteristic bands.

Result and Discussion

XRD analysis

X-ray diffraction profile of samples can provide important information in qualitative phase analysis, quantitative phase analysis, determination of unit cell parameters, study of preferred orientation, and determination of particle size. Fig.1 shows the XRD pattern of CoFe₂O₄ characteristic peaks is matches to JCPDS file no -22-1086[14]. The XRD pattern of CoFe₂O₄ corresponding structure of lattice is cubic spinel and gooddetermine at (220),(311),(222),(400),(422),(511) and (500) reflections are XRD patterns in fig.1 No extra impurity is found.

From debye-scherrer formula

$$d = 0.89 \frac{\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta}$$

where λ is a X ray wavelength and θ is a braggs angle. We have evaluated particle size from most intensity peak (311) full thickness half maximum. The mean size of particle is 15-25 μ m. Fig. 1 showed CoFe₂O₄ crystalline phase of nanoparticles by exactly similar peaks. The XRD result identified characteristic CoFe₂O₄ by major peak (311) sample almost $2\theta=35.390$ which is most important major peak of cubic spinel. The result shows that reaction temperature 353K is preferable for growth of cobalt ferrite crystallite. All the peaks recorded single phase spinel structure and no one more phase is observed.

Fig.1: XRD pattern of the prepared (CoFe₂O₄) cobalt ferrite particles.

Fig 2: SEM images of Cobalt Ferrite and (CoFe₂O₄) nanoparticles.

Fig 3: EDS image of prepared cobalt ferrite nanoparticles.

Element	Weight%	Atomic%
O K	42.00	72.00
FeK	39.06	19.18
Co k	18.94	8.82
Totals	100.00	

SEM and EDX

The morphology and particle size of as-prepared CoFe₂O₄ particle synthesized by chemical coprecipitation method investigated by using SEM micrograph as shown in fig 2. The SEM images reveal the morphology and microscopic structure of ferrite nanoparticles which are in agreement with the XRD results. The images imply considerable degree of agglomeration of ferrite particles due to its magnetic

nature and the combination of primary particles held together by weak surface interaction such as the vander Waals forces.

From SEM images it also observed that particles are distributed non uniformly.

The elemental analysis of the CoFe₂O₄ nano ferrite samples was done by Energy dispersive spectrometer

(EDS). The product of CoFe_2O_4 of all the compositions has been determined by the EDS and the patterns obtained are shown in Fig.3 shows the presence of Co, O, Fe. A quantitative EDS analysis is used to calculate the composition of CoFe_2O_4 particle. The result shown in molar ratio of CoFe_2O_4 is about 1:2.1:3.8 which ostensible composition.

Conclusion

Cobalt ferrite nanoparticle have been successfully synthesised using simple co-precipitation technique at 80°C . XRD pattern and SEM micrographs shows crystallinity and spinal structure of sample. The average particle size estimated by XRD is 20 nm. The XRD and EDS result shows the quantitative sample analysis and sample is in pure phase.

Conflicts of interest: The authors stated that no conflicts of interest.

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